

Between Clinic and Cradle: Parenting Perspectives from Paediatric-Oncologists

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the parenting experience of three paediatric oncologists raising their children in a supportive home environment and treating children with cancer professionally. The analysis uses Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (I.P.A.) to identify Five Superordinate Themes : Emotional regulation and coping in high-stress professional roles; Blurring, enmeshment, and compartmentalization of personal and professional boundaries; Relational strain and disrupted attachment in professional contexts; Professional identity, values and commitment; Ethical complexity and emotional conflict in clinical practice and Thirteen Sub-ordinate Themes : Emotion suppression and introjected tough-mindedness as part of coping; Emotional toll arising from profession and coping without systemic support; Managing empathy without losing objectivity; Emotional impact of profession; Blurriness in personal & professional life; Compartmentalization of personal and professional life; Enmeshed boundary between professional learning and parenthood; Emotional attachment and parental empathy influencing professional boundaries; Ruptured attachment formation; Professional demands & hazards; Priority, skills, interests and commitment towards profession; Societal expectation and cultural differences adding to professional stress; Medical decision-making and ethical complexity and associated emotional dilemmas. The findings have been discussed in terms of Quality of life, psychological well-being of the healthcare professional and Apprehension about the well-being of their offspring.

Keywords:

Parenting, Childhood Cancer, Paediatric-oncologist, IPA, attachment issues.

Introduction

Childhood cancers are devastating illnesses that cause profound distress for children and their families, both at diagnosis and throughout treatment. Despite advances in medicine, cancer remains one of the leading causes of death among children worldwide. Mental health professionals have been working closely with paediatric oncology teams for over 35 years, contributing to understanding the impact of cancer on children and their families. Key areas of collaboration include managing procedural pain, understanding neuropsychological impacts, treating children within their family and social contexts, applying a

developmental perspective, identifying competencies and vulnerabilities in children, integrating psychological knowledge into clinical decisions, and supporting transitions to palliative care and bereavement [1]. Parenting, a personal and transformative journey, carries additional complexity for paediatric oncologists, who face the dual perspective of being caregivers to seriously ill children and parents to their own children. Supporting patients throughout their cancer journey and facing end-of-life care can lead to intense emotional and moral distress, impacting their personal and professional identities [2]. The study aims to explore the subjective experiences of oncologists as parents, focusing on perception of a child's

well-being, family life quality, changes in professional life after a child's death, and psychological well-being associated with their job. A qualitative approach was adopted, considering the unique experiences of each individual and the social context.

Methods

Operational Definition of Key Constructs

For this study, Paediatric oncologists have been constructed to be –

(a) a licensed medical doctor specialised in diagnosing and treating cancers in children, adolescents, and young adults [3].

Sampling and Selection of Participants

Using purposive sampling, 3 participants were selected after an initial screening such that the participants have been into practising paediatric oncology for the past 3 years and have at least one child between the ages of 3 and 19 years, heading from a congenial family and the child having no significant medical or psychiatric illness.

The final sample consisted of 3 participants: Participant 1 – Dr. S.P.C. (Male with a 4-year-old male child)

Participant 2 – Dr. S.P. (Male with a 5-year-old male child)

Participant 3 – Dr. R.B. (Male with a 17-year-old male child)

Procedure

The interview schedule was prepared keeping in mind the aim and objectives. After an initial screening, informed consent was obtained from the participants, and they were then asked to fill in their sociodemographic details, following which rapport was established to ensure they felt comfortable sharing their deeply personal experiences.

Following this, data were collected through a semi-structured interview conducted for each participant. The consequent data was transcribed and analysed using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (open code, focus code, sub-theme and superordinate theme), due to its ability to help understand the participants' lived experiences, their phenomenological world, as well as the researchers' interpretation. The data was transcribed by the researcher, and the data

was simultaneously coded and interpreted by two researchers. Only those codes and/or themes were sustained that were corroborated by both researchers. Then, the emergent themes were further interpreted in the discussion section.

Result and Analysis

This section summarises the data that emerged from three in-depth individual interviews. Data analysed using interpretative phenomenological analysis. The researchers carefully coded the transcripts and identified key patterns, which were grouped into themes and broader categories. Below is a summary of the main themes that emerged:

Emotional Regulation and Coping in High-Stress Professional Roles

Emotion suppression and Introjected tough-mindedness as part of coping

One participant shares how, over time, emotional detachment became his way of coping, seeing children strictly as patients, avoiding personal bonds to protect himself and maintain professional boundaries in an emotionally taxing role.

“Being emotionally detached has a lot of advantages in my profession.... Even though my patient is a child, to me he or she is just my patient.”

Emotional toll arising from the profession and coping without systemic support.

The participant shared how each child's death leaves a deep emotional imprint. Without institutional support, coping becomes a solitary task, especially in India, where time to grieve or recover remains a rare privilege.

“We do not forget deaths. I remember all my patients who died.... I had a colleague in the UK who took a sabbatical for 3 months after a patient of hers died. Here, but sabbatical is a privilege”

Emotional impact of the profession

The participant reflected on the quiet emotional weight of their work—how loss, worry, and sleepless nights gradually wear them down.

“So yes, it’s a child and we get heavily involved....there is nothing more satisfying than curing a child Eventually, time is the best healer....It does affect quality of life, yes, worries, anxieties, sleeplessness”

Blurring, Enmeshment and Compartmentalisation of Personal and Professional Boundaries

Blurriness in personal and professional life

This narrative highlights how professional concerns often spill into personal life. The participant carries the weight of critically ill patients’ homes, where medical instincts blur with parental fears.

“...I think about them, even at home, about their well-being and how to provide better care... But that hasn’t affected my relationship with my child... in case of a recurrent illness, the worst crosses my mind, but I have never run any tests.”

Compartmentalisation of personal and professional life

This narrative reveals the participant’s effort to compartmentalise work and home life. While he strives to remain emotionally composed and focused, moments of vulnerability and quiet concern for his own child occasionally break through.

“I try to keep my office and my home on two completely different fronts But I did get overwhelmed by emotions at some point in time. I always checked up on my child from time to time. I was not very concerned, but I did that.”

Enmeshed boundary between professional learning and parenthood

This narrative reflects how parenting and professional experience intertwine. Medical knowledge sharpens his vigilance as a father, while parenting deepens his empathy as a doctor.

“I keep an eye on my child But that has not affected my relationship with him.... But paediatrics has taught me very practical aspects of childcare....my son knows that my The profession is very demanding, difficult, rather challenging....but he is very understanding and compromising”

Relational Strain and Disrupted Attachment in a Professional Context

Ruptured attachment formation

This narrative highlights the delicate balance between personal attachment and professional boundaries.

“My child is very young, so drawing, playing with him, and spending time is the only way I have to form an attachment with him – and I don’t feel I am detached from my child.... Very recently, the children in the ward celebrated my birthday, they gave me presents. I took them home, kept them for 2-3 days and then again brought them back and kept them in a place in my cabin where they would go unnoticed.”

Emotional attachment and parental empathy influencing professional boundaries

This narrative explores how being a parent enriches a doctor’s empathy, making emotional connections with patients and families almost unavoidable. While professionalism remains intact, personal experiences heighten sensitivity, especially during loss, grief, and long-term care.

“So, a parent’s relationship with their children is invariably the most precious. Patients’ death does affect us - psychologically, although we do not show If someone says they do not form attachment with their patient, I doubt that relationship... Then, as a parent yourself, you are able to understand both sides better- the parents and the child... also, it’s difficult to deal with the grieving parents “

Professional identity, values and commitment

Professional demands and hazards

This narrative highlights the emotional toll of paediatric oncology, where enduring repeated loss becomes part of the job.

“So, when I see a child die right in front of me or when I get affected for some time, but I have to move on... I have seen more than 1000 deaths in the past 13 years, and all were children.”

Priority, skills, interests and commitment towards profession

This narrative reflects a deep commitment to paediatrics, valuing the joy found in easing children's pain and bringing smiles to families.

"I'm more comfortable treating children The smile on the child's face, their parents' face, is very rewarding – and that is very important for me.... I also want to work on raising awareness about childhood cancers.... For death counselling, breaking bad news, handling such situations, professional courses are needed."

Societal expectations and cultural differences are adding to professional stress.

This narrative reveals the added stress from societal expectations and cultural differences, where doctors often face blame despite their honesty. Despite emotional strain causing many colleagues to leave, the participant feels privileged to save children's lives and remains dedicated, working daily amid ongoing challenges.

"In India, there's a tendency to blame the doctor, which is difficult to handleIf they feel something's wrong, they can question, but it must be decent. Because of unpleasant reactions, the medical fraternity avoids risks and the quality of care and medical progress suffer..."

Ethical complexity and emotional conflict in clinical practice

Managing empathy without losing objectivity

One participant shared how they balance deep empathy with staying composed, knowing that parents rely on their strength during tough moments like a child's death.

"Caring for children who are on their deathbed needs a lot of empathy, but again, try not to blur my judgement or put myself in the parent's seat..... So, you must have full control over your emotions...the grieving parents look up to you for support..."

Medical decision-making and ethical complexity, and associated emotional dilemmas

This narrative reveals the emotional and

ethical challenges in paediatric oncology. The participant stresses honest communication with families and making tough, compassionate decisions daily.

"As oncologists, we have to be open and honest... Families expect complete honesty....maintaining contact afterwards helps answer unanswered questions. In India, contact often ends with the child's death.... No doctor wants harm to their patient-sometimes things are beyond our control.... I don't think my professional life impacts my relationship with my child."

Discussion

This study explores how paediatric oncologists who are also parents navigate the emotional demands of both roles. Despite different backgrounds, their shared struggles revealed thirteen subordinate and five superordinate themes, showing how their work shapes and tests their identities as parents.

Emotional Regulation and Coping in High-Stress Professional Roles

Working in paediatric oncology means walking a tightrope. These doctors care deeply for children and families, yet they must also protect their emotional core to keep doing the work. One oncologist described deliberately holding back from forming deep bonds with patients, not out of coldness, but to survive emotionally. This reflects what Gross [4] calls emotional suppression, a way professionals mask emotions to stay functional.

In high-stakes care like this, such coping can evolve into what Kohut [5] called "introjected tough-mindedness", the quiet pressure to be strong, despite circumstances. Hochschild's [6] idea of emotional labour is central here: caregivers must manage feelings under adverse conditions. Psychodynamic theories help understand this further. Freud [7] viewed suppression as a way to keep painful feelings out of consciousness. Bowlby's [8] attachment theory suggests that those with early experiences of loss or uncertainty may become emotionally cautious later in a pattern echoed in some oncologists'

emotional distance.

Despite these efforts to cope, the emotional weight is real. One doctor recalled every child they had lost, each memory sharp, painful, unforgettable. This is the emotional cost of care, often described as compassion fatigue [9]. The need to suppress grief and “carry on” mirrors the burnout described by many researchers [10], particularly when institutions fail to support their staff's mental health.

Empathy is vital in medicine, but too much can be paralyzing. Some participants spoke about the risk of getting too emotionally close, which aligns with Decety and Jackson's [11] concept of empathic distress [12].

As Freud [13] would say, the emotional distance these doctors adopt is often a “compromise formation”, a way to function in the face of overwhelming pressure. Bowlby [14] would likely call it adaptive avoidance, a survival strategy.

Still, many find ways to shift perspective. One oncologist said they focused on the children cured rather than the ones not cured. This is what Folkman and Moskowitz [15] call positive reappraisal, a kind of emotional reframing that brings resilience. Yet even with this mindset, the emotional toll shows up in sleepless nights and anxiety.

Blurring, Enmeshment and Compartmentalisation of Personal and Professional Boundaries

For many paediatric oncologists, work doesn't end when they leave the hospital. The emotional echoes follow them home, especially for those who are parents themselves. One participant described becoming overly alert to their own child's symptoms, revealing what Ashforth [16] calls boundary permeability when the lines between work and personal life become thin. Another shared how their roles as parent and doctor often blended, a phenomenon Clark [17] describes as role integration. When a parent-doctor treats a sick child, they may unconsciously respond not just as a clinician, but as a parent. Bowlby [18] would suggest this blurring is shaped by deep-seated caregiving instincts.

To cope, many adopt compartmentalisation, consciously separating work from home [19]. This aligns with Freud's [20] concept of “isolation of affect,” where thoughts and emotions are separated to protect the psyche. Sonnentag and Fritz [21] note that this strategy can aid emotional recovery, though it's not always easy.

For some, however, being a parent deepened their empathy. They related more intuitively to families and spent extra time supporting parents. This empathy isn't just professional, it's personal. Bowlby [8] would say the caregiving system gets activated beyond one's own children.

These connections often linger beyond treatment. Many participants stay in touch with bereaved families. Freud's [23] grief theory suggests that deeply felt attachments take time to release. These clinicians don't just treat disease; they witness suffering, build bonds, and sometimes grieve alongside families. But in doing so, they carry emotional weight that is often invisible to those outside the profession.

Relational Strain and Disrupted Attachment in Professional Contexts

Emotional exhaustion doesn't just stay at work—it spills into relationships at home. One oncologist shared that their fatigue made it difficult to bond with their own child. Bowlby [18] argued that children need emotionally available caregivers; in high-stress professions, this availability can be compromised.

To reconnect, some turn to small acts of intimacy, drawing, playing, storytelling. These efforts reflect Bowlby's idea of creating a safe base for connection, even when time and energy are limited.

Other participants spoke about receiving emotional tokens—letters, drawings, or gifts—but holding back their reactions. They felt deeply but didn't show it. These strategies mirror Ainsworth's (1978)[24] avoidant attachment style—a protective mechanism in emotionally overwhelming environments.

One oncologist shared how becoming a parent reshaped their clinical empathy. Their personal experiences enriched their

understanding, helping them notice subtle psychosocial cues—like a child’s missed schooling or social struggles. This reflects Ickes’ [25] empathic accuracy, the ability to read others’ emotional states with depth. But greater sensitivity also means greater emotional burden. Freud [13] would describe this as a conflict between the id (emotion), ego (reason), and superego (duty), a constant balancing act that takes its toll.

Professional Identity, Values and Commitment

Paediatric oncologists don’t just do a job—they live a vocation. Their professional identity is deeply tied to purpose, values, and emotional resilience.

One doctor reflected on how grief appears only briefly before being pushed aside as a necessity, not a choice. But this distancing, if prolonged, risks emotional numbness and burnout (Vaillant, 1992) [26].

Another participant described the inability to socialise or form attachments as beneficial. While this may reflect Bowlby’s [17] defensive detachment, it also signals emotional exhaustion. Moral dilemmas, especially when treating terminal cases, intensify this distress [27]. Yet others described their work as joyful and meaningful, especially the bonds they form with children. This sense of calling [28] is a powerful counterforce to stress. Freud [29] would call this sublimation, transforming difficult emotions into purposeful action.

Several participants mentioned how working with children so open and trusting offered a unique emotional reward [30]. Their research and advocacy efforts echo Cruess’s [31] model of professional identity, rooted in service and excellence.

Still, many grapple with cultural and systemic pressures. One participant shared the fear of being blamed or attacked, a growing issue in India’s healthcare environment [32]. Hofstede [33] notes that high power distance and low ambiguity tolerance fuel distrust, making open communication difficult.

Even so, the smallest victories, a life saved, a call of thanks, remind these doctors why they do what they do. Frankl [34] wrote that

meaning helps us endure suffering. And for these oncologists, meaning is often found in fleeting moments of connection. Yet everyone acknowledged their limits. All spoke of breaking points, times when the emotional toll felt too much. Taking a break or seeking support is often seen as a luxury in India’s strained system. Without better institutional structures, burnout remains a looming threat [35].

Ethical Complexity and Emotional Conflict in Clinical Practice

The work of paediatric oncologists is full of moral complexity. They walk a fine line between feeling deeply and making rational decisions. One participant said it plainly: putting yourself in the parents’ shoes can cloud your judgment. Halpern would agree that while empathy is vital, it must be balanced [36].

Being honest with families, even when the truth is devastating, takes enormous emotional strength. It reflects the ethical principle of autonomy [37], but it’s also one of the hardest parts of the job.

Many go beyond what’s required, attending funerals, staying in touch, offering emotional support long after treatment ends. This reflects a relational ethics approach [38], where care is rooted in connection, not just protocol. They try to share decisions with families [39], but grief, culture, and communication barriers often make this hard. Reflecting on these decisions, whether in solitude or with peers, helps them grow. Schön’s [40] idea of reflective practice is key.

In India, where talking openly about death is often taboo, these conversations become even harder. Some clinicians teach their own children about death not to frighten them, but to prepare them [41].

Conclusion

This study offers a rare glimpse into the lives of paediatric oncologists who are also parents, balancing clinical grief and hope daily. Their stories show how emotional suppression helps them cope but often leads to burnout. Meaningful connections sustain them, yet without proper support, even

resilience falters. Recognising emotional labour as real labour and embedding mental health care in medical culture is essential. This research invites us to see doctors not just as professionals, but as people, urging a more compassionate, human-centred healthcare system.

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Declaration of competing interests

No conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

References

1. Wiener L, Alderfer M A, & Pao M. Psychosocial care of the paediatric oncology patient undergoing surgical treatment. *Oncohematol Key*. 2013.
2. Bauer-Wu S. The role of the paediatric-oncologist in supporting families: A qualitative study. *Journal of Paediatric Oncology Nursing*. 2013; 30(3):135-142.
3. Tan A, Long K A, & Marsland A L. Parenting while practicing paediatric oncology: A qualitative exploration of dual roles. *Psycho-Oncology*. 2020; 29(12):2051–2058.
4. Gross J J. Emotion regulation: Affective, cognitive, and social consequences. *Psychophysiology*. 200; 39(3):281–291.
5. Kohut H. *The restoration of the self*. International Universities Press. 1977.
6. Hochschild A R. *The managed heart: Commercialization of human feeling*. University of California Press. 1983.
7. Freud S. *Inhibitions, symptoms and anxiety*. Hogarth Press. 1926/1959.
8. Bowlby J. *Attachment and loss: Vol. 1. Attachment*. Basic Books. 1969.
9. Figureley C R. *Compassion fatigue: Coping with secondary traumatic stress disorder in those who treat the traumatized*. Brunner/Mazel. 1995.
10. Maslach C, Schaufeli W B & Leiter M P. Job burnout. *Annual Review of Psychology*. 2001; 52(1):397-422.
11. Decety J & Jackson P L. The functional architecture of human empathy. *Behavioral and Cognitive Neuroscience Reviews*. 2004; 3(2):71-100.
12. Baron-Cohen S & Wheelwright S. The empathy quotient: An investigation of adults with Asperger syndrome or high functioning autism, and normal sex differences. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*. 2004; 34(2):163-175.
13. Freud S. *The ego and the id*. Hogarth Press. 1923/1961.
14. Bowlby J. *Attachment and loss: Vol. 3. Loss, sadness and depression*. Basic Books. 1980.
15. Folkman S & Moskowitz J T. Positive affect and the other side of coping. *American Psychologist*. 2000; 55(6):647-654.
16. Ashforth B E, Kreiner G E & Fugate M. All in a day's work: Boundaries and micro role transitions. *Academy of Management Review*. 2000; 25(3):472–491.
17. Clark S C. *Work/family border theory: A new theory of work/family balance*. *Human Relations*. 2000; 53(6):747–770.
18. Bowlby J. *A secure base: Parent-child attachment and healthy human development*. Basic Books. 1988.
19. Nippert-Eng C. *Home and work: Negotiating boundaries through everyday life*. University of Chicago Press. 1996.
20. Freud A. *The ego and the mechanisms of defense*. International Universities Press. 1936/1959.
21. Sonnentag S & Fritz C. Recovery from job stress: The stressor-detachment model as an integrative framework. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*. 2015; 36(S1): S72–S103.
22. Freud S. *The dynamics of transference*. Hogarth Press. 1912/1958.
23. Freud S. *Mourning and melancholia*. Hogarth Press. 1917/1957.
24. Ainsworth M D S, Blehar M C, Waters E & Wall S. *Patterns of attachment: A psychological study of the strange situation*. Lawrence Erlbaum

- Associates. 1978.
25. Ickes W. Empathic accuracy. Guilford Press. 1997.
 26. Vaillant G E. Ego mechanisms of defence: A guide for clinicians and researchers. American Psychiatric Press. 1992.
 27. Epstein E G & Hamric A B. Moral distress, moral residue, and the crescendo effect, *The Journal of Clinical Ethics*. 2009; 20(4):330–342.
 28. Wrzesniewski A, McCauley C, Rozin P & Schwartz B. Jobs, careers, and callings: People's relations to their work, *Journal of Research in Personality*. 1997; 31(1):21–33.
 29. Freud S. On narcissism: An introduction. Hogarth Press. 1914/1958.
 30. Street R L, Makoul G, Arora N K & Epstein R M. How does communication heal? Pathways linking clinician–patient communication to health outcomes. *Patient Education and Counseling*. 2009; 74(3):295–301.
 31. Cruess R L, Cruess S R, Boudreau J D, Snell L & Steinert Y. A schematic representation of the professional identity formation and socialization of medical students and residents: A guide for medical educators. *Academic Medicine*. 2016; 90(6):718–725.
 32. Patel M, Porecha M & Chavda M. Violence against doctors in India: Causes and solutions. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*. 2020.
 33. Hofstede G. Culture's consequences: Comparing values, behaviors, institutions and organizations across nations. Sage Publications. 2001.
 34. Frankl V E. Man's search for meaning. Beacon Press. 1959.
 35. Shanafelt T D, Hasan O, Dyrbye L N, Sinsky C, Satele D, Sloan J, & West C P. Changes in burnout and satisfaction with work-life balance in physicians and the general US working population between 2011 and 2014. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*. 2012; 90(12):1600–1613.
 36. Halpern J. From detached concern to empathy: Humanizing medical practice. Oxford University Press. 2001.
 37. Beauchamp T L & Childress J F. Principles of biomedical ethics (7th ed.). Oxford University Press. 2013.
 38. Bergum V & Dossetor J. Relational ethics: The full meaning of respect. University Publishing Group. 2005.
 39. Charles C, Gafni A & Whelan T. Shared decision-making in the medical encounter: What does it mean? (Or it takes at least two to tango). *Social Science & Medicine*. 1997; 44(5): 681–692.
 40. Schön D A. The reflective practitioner: How professionals think in action. Basic Books. 1983.
 41. Gielen J, Bhatnagar S, Chaturvedi SK. Spirituality as an ethical challenge in Indian palliative care: A systematic review. *Palliative & supportive care*. 2016 Oct;14(5):561-8

Design, Characterisation and Evaluation Study for Immediate Release Formulation of Canagliflozin

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ABSTRACT

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is a complex metabolic disorder in which the glucose levels in the human body cannot be easily controlled due to insufficient insulin production by the pancreas. Canagliflozin is a widely used and effective drug for managing this condition, known for its safety and efficacy, with a half-life of approximately 10.6 hours. The primary objective of this study was to modify the drug release pattern to achieve an immediate release formulation, particularly for emergencies where rapid therapeutic action is required. To accomplish this, a comprehensive preformulation study was conducted, which included analytical techniques such as IR Spectra, UV-Spectrophotometry, solubility analysis, and melting point determination to evaluate the compatibility of the drug with excipients. Subsequently, formulation studies were performed using sodium starch glycolate as a special polymer in three consecutive batches to optimise the drug release profile. The in-vitro evaluation involved a detailed analysis of physical and chemical parameters, including disintegration time, dissolution studies, friability testing, and hardness measurements, using different polymer ratios to achieve the desired release characteristics. Based on the experimental findings, it was observed that the drug release time of Canagliflozin could be significantly reduced from 10 hours to just 15 minutes for 100 mg tablets through a polymer-based approach, demonstrating its potential for rapid onset of action. This study successfully establishes that Canagliflozin can be effectively formulated for immediate release, enhancing its therapeutic efficacy and providing a faster response in critical conditions, thereby improving patient outcomes in the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus.

KEYWORDS - Diabetes, Canagliflozin, Sodium glucose co-transporter, Invokana, renal, cardiac

Introduction.

The term "immediate release" (IR) describes how quickly a product, medication, or piece of information becomes available following administration or announcement. In medicine, it indicates that the medication dissolves rapidly for a prompt effect. This term in the media refers to press releases intended for immediate publication. When timing is crucial, it guarantees a quick effect or communication.

Canagliflozin is an oral antidiabetic medication that belongs to the sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitor class. It is primarily used for managing type 2 diabetes mellitus by lowering blood glucose levels through a unique insulin-independent mechanism. By inhibiting

SGLT2 in the kidneys it reduces glucose reabsorption and promotes its excretion through urine, leading to improved glycemic control [1]. In addition to its glucose-lowering effects, Canagliflozin also contributes to weight loss, lowers blood pressure, and provides cardiovascular and renal benefits, making it a valuable option for patients with diabetes and associated complications. However, its use is associated with potential side effects such as an increased risk of urinary tract and genital infections, dehydration, hypotension, and, in rare cases, diabetic ketoacidosis. Some studies have also linked it to an increased risk of bone fractures due to possible reductions in bone mineral density. Despite these concerns, canagliflozin remains an important therapeutic option, particularly for patients who require additional benefits beyond